

Pilot Testing Results (n = 25)

Construct	Sub-Construct / Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach's α	Decision / Interpretation
Waste Management Practices	Reduce	5	0.78	Acceptable reliability
	Reuse	5	0.81	Good reliability
	Recycle	5	0.79	Acceptable reliability
	Recover / Dispose	5	0.82	Good reliability
Eco-Guilt	Emotional Discomfort	5	0.84	Good reliability
	Awareness of Consequences	5	0.87	Good reliability
	Moral Accountability	5	0.85	Good reliability
	Social Pressure Guilt	5	0.77	Acceptable reliability
Eco-Responsibility	Sense of Moral Duty	5	0.82	Good reliability
	Proactive Commitment	5	0.80	Good reliability
	Community Accountability	5	0.79	Good reliability
	Consistency of Behavior	5	0.81	Good reliability